

The emerging principle of force-sharing among actin cytoskeletal proteins

Tianzhi Luo^{1*}

¹ Department of Cell Biology, School of Medicine, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD, 21205, USA

* Corresponding author, Email: tzluo@jhu.edu

The actin cytoskeletal proteins in the cortex are the major players that sense mechanical cues and activate downstream signaling pathways (such as cell differentiation, migration and tissue morphogenesis) [1-7], as well as physiological processes (such as blood flow regulation and lung respiration) [8,9]. Additionally, the actin cytoskeleton is associated with many diseases in heart and lung [10] and governs the migration of cancer cells in these organs [11]. Great effort has been invested in understanding the significance of the actin cytoskeleton from molecular to cellular to tissue levels [3, 12-14]. Most of these studies were focused on cell-substrate interactions and associated signaling pathways. Among them, the formation of stress fibers and focal adhesions were popularly investigated [15-17]. Importantly, several recent reports revealed the molecular behaviors of non-muscle myosin II [18], talin [19] and vinculin. Together with the cellular characterization mentioned above, numerous studies on *in vitro* actin network originated a physical concept of force-sharing among the cytoskeletal proteins regarding the microstructure of actin meshwork [20-29]. Before elucidate this concept, it is useful to revisit the microstructures and mechanical properties of actin cortex in cells.

One popular structural model for the cell is to assume that it has a cortical shell consisting of the actin cortex and plasma membrane, which encapsulates an inner, largely viscous cytoplasm (with organelles). The cell membrane and the underlying actin cortex may be considered a membrane-cortex composite (Fig. A). The cell membrane is composed of bilayer of lipid molecules and contributes to the bending rigidity of the composite [30]. On the other hand, the actin cortex, with a thickness ranging from a few hundred nanometers to one micron, dominates the in-plane stretch modulus of the composite. The actin cortex has a network structure, consisting of proteins such as actin, actin crosslinkers (ACs), and myosin II. As a motor protein, myosin II, binds to actin filaments and pulls them to provide internal contractile force. The ACs organize individual actin filaments into structures such as bundles and meshwork [26,31], whose relative abundance is determined by the relative concentrations of two classes of ACs [28]. Meanwhile, anchoring proteins bridge the actin cortex to the plasma membrane to form the membrane-cortex composite.

During deformation, all proteins in the actin cortex share the external load while the plasma membrane mainly provides the resistance to bending deformation. The mechanical properties of the actin cortex depend on the force-dependent affinities of all of these proteins for F-actin and their concentrations [23,24]. According to force-sharing concept, a first order approximation of the Young's modulus of cellular cortex E could be

$$E = E_{actin} + a_0 C_{myo}^{n_0} + a_1 C_1^{n_1} + \dots + a_k C_k^{n_k}$$

Equation 1

In this equation, the subscript $i=0, \dots, k$ denotes different ACs. The coefficients a_i contain the information of the force-dependent affinity of the proteins to F-actin, superscript n_i is an exponential denoting cooperativity, and C_i is the protein concentration in the cell cortex. Similarly, E_{actin} also depends on the concentration of F-actin. Here, higher order terms for the cooperative and antagonistic interactions among these proteins are neglected for the time being. Eq. (1) indicates the structure of actin cortex can be considered an apparatus consisting of parallel springs where each spring represents one kind of ACs besides myosin II (Fig. B).

The amount of force shared by different proteins has a similar form:

$$F_{total} = F_{actin} + F_{myo} + F_1 + \dots + F_k$$

Equation 2

where F_{actin} and F_{myo} , are the forces carried on by actin filament and myosin II, respectively; the terms F_i are the forces on the i th ACs. If all the actin filaments are short than 500 nm, they only transmit force with negligible deformation according to nonlinear elasticity theory [32,33]. In this case, F_{actin} is close to zero. The depletion of any ACs is supposed to reduce the Young's modulus of the cell cortex and consequently distribute the amount of force (initially the depleted ACs subjected to) among the remaining proteins (Fig. C). When cells deform under external load, the force-sharing principle requires the maintenance of physical linkages between the actin cortex and the plasma membrane. Damage to these linkages presumably disrupt the force propagation from the membrane to the cortex and hence reduce the forces applied on the actin cytoskeletal proteins.

Figure Schematic graphs of force-sharing concept in the interactions among cytoskeletal proteins. (A) A cell deformed by micropipette aspiration where blue bundles are myosin-II thick filament, green ones are actin crosslinkers, and orange filaments are actin filaments. (B) A mechanical apparatus consists of parallel springs mimicking the actin cytoskeletal proteins under applied forces. (C) One of the crosslinker (X-linker 1) is genetically depleted or pharmacologically inhibited and forces are redistributed among the rest proteins compared to the scenario in (B).

One can actually implement this force-sharing principle numerically into coarse-grained molecular simulations to predict how actin network (or cytoskeleton-membrane composite) remodels under load [14,22,29]. Especially, when the actin network consists of ACs with either catch-bond or slip-bond behaviors at different force regime [34-37], the remodeling exhibits different interesting phenomena, such as protein clustering [22] and accumulation [14,], as well as pattern formation [29]. These simulated results actually reproduce the major features of experimental observations.

Accumulating evidence demonstrates that the combination of molecular behaviors of cytoskeletal proteins and force-sharing principle is a useful tool to facilitate the understandings of many biological phenomena at cellular and tissue levels. It enables more quantitative *in silico* predictions in our future research.

References

- Geiger B, Spatz JP, Bershadsky AD: Environmental sensing through focal adhesions. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2009, 10: 21-33
- Wang N, Tytell JD, Ingber DE: Mechanotransduction at a distance: mechanically coupling the extracellular matrix with the nucleus. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2009, 10: 75-82
- Wang Y, Botvinick EL, Zhao Y, Berns MW, Usami S, et al.: Visualizing the mechanical activation of Src. *Nature* 2005, 434: 1040-1045
- Howard J, Grill SW, Bois JS: Turing's next steps: the mechanochemical basis of morphogenesis. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2011, 12: 392-398
- Dahmann C, Oates AC, Brand M: Boundary formation and maintenance in tissue development. *Nat Rev Genet* 2011, 12: 43-55

- Engler AJ, Sen S, Sweeney HL, Discher DE: Matrix elasticity directs stem cell lineage specification. *Cell* 2006, 126: 677-689
- Vicente-Manzanares M, Ma X, Adelstein RS, Horwitz AR: Non-muscle myosin II takes centre stage in cell adhesion and migration. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2009, 10: 778-790
- Prosser BL, Ward CW, Lederer WJ: X-ROS signaling: rapid mechanochemo transduction in heart. *Science* 2011, 333: 1440-5
- Knöll R, Hoshijima M, Chien K: Cardiac mechanotransduction and implications for heart disease. *J Mol Med (Berl)* 2003, 81: 750-756
- Jaalouk DE, Lammerding J: Mechanotransduction gone awry. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2009, 10: 63-73
- Friedl P, Gilmour D: Collective cell migration in morphogenesis, regeneration and cancer. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2009, 10: 445-457
- He L, Wang X, Tang HL, Montell DJ: Tissue elongation requires oscillating contractions of a basal actomyosin network. *Nat Cell Biol* 2010, 12: 1133-1142
- Sawada Y, Tamada M, Dubin-Thaler BJ, Cherniavskaya O, Sakai R, et al.: Force sensing by mechanical extension of the Src family kinase substrate p130Cas. *Cell* 2006, 127: 1015-1026
- T Luo, K Mohan, PA Iglesias, DN Robinson: Molecular mechanisms of cellular mechanosensing *Nature Materials* 2013, 12, 1064-1071
- Tan JL, Tien J, Pirone DM, Gray DS, Bhadriraju K, et al.: Cells lying on a bed of microneedles: an approach to isolate mechanical force. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 100:1484-9
- Kaunas R, Nguyen P, Usami S, Chien S: Cooperative effects of Rho and mechanical stretch on stress fiber organization. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2005, 102: 15895-15900
- Grashoff C, Hoffman BD, Brenner MD, Zhou R, Parsons M, et al.: Measuring mechanical tension across vinculin reveals regulation of focal adhesion dynamics. *Nature* 2010, 466: 263-266
- Kovács M, Thirumurugan K, Knight PJ, Sellers JR: Load-dependent mechanism of nonmuscle myosin 2. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2007, 104: 9994-9999
- del Rio A, Perez-Jimenez R, Liu R, Roca-Cusachs P, Fernandez JM, et al.: Stretching single talin rod molecules activates vinculin binding. *Science* 2009, 323: 638-641
- Koenderink GH, Atakhorrami M, MacKintosh FC, Schmidt CF: High-frequency stress relaxation in semiflexible polymer solutions and networks. *Phys Rev Lett* 2006, 96: 138307
- Koenderink GH, Dogic Z, Nakamura F, Bendix PM, MacKintosh FC, et al.: An active biopolymer network controlled by molecular motors. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2009, 106: 15192-15197
- Alvarado J, Sheinman M, Sharma A, MacKintosh FC, Koenderink GH: *Nat Phys* 2013,
- Gardel ML, Shin JH, MacKintosh FC, Mahadevan L, Matsudaira P, et al.: Elastic behavior of cross-linked and bundled actin networks. *Science* 2004, 304: 1301-1305
- Shin JH, Gardel ML, Mahadevan L, Matsudaira P, Weitz DA: Relating microstructure to rheology of a bundled and cross-linked F-actin network *in vitro*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2004, 101: 9636-9641
- Gardel ML, Nakamura F, Hartwig JH, Crocker JC, Stossel TP, et al.: Prestressed F-actin networks cross-linked by hinged filamins replicate mechanical properties of cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006, 103: 1762-1767
- Wagner B, Tharmann R, Haase I, Fischer M, Bausch AR: Cytoskeletal polymer networks: the molecular structure of cross-linkers determines macroscopic properties. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006, 103: 13974-13978
- Claessens MM, Bathe M, Frey E, Bausch AR: Actin-binding proteins sensitively mediate F-actin bundle stiffness. *Nat Mater* 2006, 5: 748-753
- Schmoller KM, Lieleg O, Bausch AR: Cross-linking molecules modify composite actin networks independently. *Phys Rev Lett* 2008, 101: 118102
- Köhler S, Schaller V, Bausch AR: Structure formation in active networks. *Nat Mater* 2011, 10: 462-468
- Discher DE, Boal DH, Boey SK: Simulations of the erythrocyte cytoskeleton at large deformation. II. Micropipette aspiration. *Biophys J* 1998, 75: 1584-1597
- Gardel ML, Nakamura F, Hartwig JH, Crocker JC, Stossel TP, et al.: Prestressed F-actin networks cross-linked by hinged filamins replicate mechanical properties of cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006, 103: 1762-1767
- Storm C, Pastore JJ, MacKintosh FC, Lubensky TC, Janmey PA: Nonlinear elasticity in biological gels. *Nature* 2005, 435: 191-194
- Palmer JS, Boyce MC: Constitutive modeling of the stress-strain behavior of F-actin filament networks. *Acta Biomater* 2008, 4: 597-612
- Ferrer JM, Lee H, Chen J, Pelz B, Nakamura F, et al.: Measuring molecular rupture forces between single actin filaments and actin-binding proteins. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2008, 105: 9221-9226

35. Norman YY, Chase PB, Martin D, Daniel JB, Martin RP, et al.: Stress-enhanced Gelation: A Dynamic Nonlinearity of Elasticity. *Phys Rev Lett* 2013, 110 :018103
36. Guo B, Guilford WH: Mechanics of actomyosin bonds in different nucleotide states are tuned to muscle contraction. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006, 103: 9844-9849
37. Thomas WE, Vogel V, Sokurenko E: Biophysics of catch bonds. *Annu Rev Biophys* 2008, 37: 399-416